

Little Learners

Rosario M. Pepito

They come to me small with their stories untold,
Some shy as a whisper, some loud and so bold.
A scraped little knee and a tooth that came loose,
A question of why is the sky not bright puce,
And every small wonder is purer than gold.

I kneel to their level, I meet every face,
For learning takes patience and kindness and space.
I teach them their letters, their numbers, their ways,
But mostly I teach them their own worth of praise,
And send them off braver to grow at their pace.

They squabble at recess, they share and they cry,
They marvel at beetles that crawl, ants that fly.
A circle of carpet, a song, and a book,
And forty bright eyes give me all that they took,
The trust of a child is a gift I live by.

And some of them struggle and some of them race,
But none of them travels the very same pace.
So I hold the slow ones with extra-warm hands,
And stretch the quick minds into wider new lands,
For each little learner deserves their own grace.

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